

Limitations on the Low Frequency Range of Pulsed, Thick Piezoelectric Disks

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Abstract - The objective of this paper is to determine the useful low-frequency limit for transiently-excited thick transducers. The Redwood representation of the Mason equivalent circuit was analyzed for times less than the acoustic propagation time through the transducer. This propagation time, t_T , is the maximum interval available for measuring the pressure pulse radiated from the transducer's front face. In applications such as finding the frequency dependence of hydrophone sensitivity, the reciprocal of t_T sets an approximate lower limit on the useful frequency range when using the thick-transducer technique. A second low-frequency limit is the reciprocal of the transducer time constant, a quantity arising from the negative capacitance that appears in the transducer equivalent circuit. For common transducer materials and dimensions, these factors set a usable lower limit of 200-400 kHz.

I. INTRODUCTION

When the duration of the electrical pulse exciting a thickness-expansion (TE) mode piezoelectric transducer is much less than the time it takes for the mechanical wave to travel through the transducer, four distinct pressure pulses are radiated by the transducer, two from the front face into the transducer and load, and two from the rear face into the transducer and backing [1], [2]. If the propagation time through the transducer is called t_T , then for times $0 \leq t < t_T$ the pressure field in the load comprises solely the initial front face pressure pulse, $p_f(t)$ (neglecting finite aperture effects).

Under these conditions the temporal shape and spectral content of $p_f(t)$ can be approximated from a measurement of the electrical excitation pulse, $v_T(t)$.

This result has proven useful in a number of applications, such as determining the broadband frequency response of miniature ultrasonic hydrophones [3], [4]. However, one aspect of the technique that has received little attention is the lower frequency range for which the approximation is valid. This low-frequency limit was examined by modeling the transducer using the Redwood representation of the Mason equivalent circuit [1]. Two factors were found that restrict the low frequency range of the technique, one related to the transducer time constant and one to the transducer transit time, t_T .

II. EFFECTS AT LOW FREQUENCIES

A. Transducer Time Constant

For times $0 \leq t < t_T$ the Redwood equivalent circuit for a TE-mode transducer can be solved to give the following expression for $p_f(t)$.

$$p_f(t) \propto v_T(t) + \omega_T e^{\omega_T t} \int_0^t v_T(\tau) e^{-\omega_T \tau} d\tau, \quad (1)$$

where $(\omega_T)^{-1} = (2\pi f_T)^{-1}$ is the transducer time constant, a quantity that arises when the electrical and acoustic axes are aligned, as they are in a TE-

mode transducer. This time constant is related to the negative capacitance that appears in the equivalent circuit. For an air-backed transducer radiating into water, ω_T is approximately equal to $he/\pi z_T x_T$, where h and e are piezoelectric stress constants, and z_T and x_T are the transducer characteristic impedance and thickness.

The regenerative action associated with ω_T results in the positive exponential term in (1). Because of this rising exponential, the Fourier transform of (1) does not exist along the real frequency axis. The only practical means for circumventing this problem is to restrict the analysis to frequencies such that $f \gg f_T$, in which case the pressure spectrum can be obtained from the Fourier transform of the transducer voltage, $v_T(t)$. For the piezoceramic disk transducer used in [3], $f_T = 15$ kHz, and for the lithium niobate disk of [4], $f_T = 3$ kHz.

B. Transducer Transit Time

Because (1) is valid only for times less than t_T , there is a finite measurement time available using the thick transducer technique. In a hydrophone frequency response measurement, if the hydrophone signal, $v_H(t)$, in response to $p_i(t)$ persists longer than t_T , then windowing of $v_H(t)$ will be necessary.

The effect of such windowing at low frequencies was examined using the approach depicted in Fig. 1. Here the pressure pulse $p_i(t)$ with spectrum $P_i(f)$ is received by the hydrophone having response $H(f)$. The hydrophone output $V_H(f)$ is then convolved with the window function spectrum $W(f)$ to produce $V_{HW}(f)$. That is,

$$\begin{aligned} V_{HW}(f) &= V_H(f) * W(f) = [P_i(f) \cdot H(f)] * W(f) \\ &= P_i(f) \cdot H_w(f), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $*$ denotes convolution, and $H_w(f)$ represents

the measured hydrophone response after windowing.

Figure 1 - Diagram of model used to determine effect of windowing on measurement of hydrophone response, $H(f)$.

The problem is to see how the desired response, $H(f) = V_H(f)/P_i(f)$, compares to $H_w(f) = V_{HW}(f)/P_i(f)$, especially at low frequencies. This was done by modeling $H(f)$ as a single-pole, high-pass filter [5], and letting $p_i(t)$ (now assumed equivalent to $v_T(t)$) be a narrow ($< 1 \mu s$) Gaussian pulse, similar to that generated experimentally in [6]. Also, for window function $w(t)$ a rectangular pulse with a duration of $5 \mu s$ was used.

$H_w(f)$ was compared to $H(f)$ as the -3 dB cutoff frequency for $H(f)$, f_{CO} , was varied from 20-400 kHz in steps of 20 kHz. A normalized RMS error (RMSE) for the magnitude response was computed as

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (|H_w(i\Delta f)| - |H(i\Delta f)|)^2}{\sum_{i=0}^N |H(i\Delta f)|^2}}, \quad (3)$$

where $N\Delta f = 500$ kHz. Values of (3) for a Gaussian pulse having a duration of $0.5 \mu s$ (at 0.001 of its peak) are given in Table I. Note that

TABLE I

RMS Error (RMSE) vs $H(f)$ High-pass Cutoff Frequency f_{CO} for 0.5- μ s Gaussian Pulse, $p_t(t)$.

f_{CO} (kHz)	40	80	120	160	200	240	280	320	360	400
RMSE (%)	9.9	4.5	1.8	0.68	0.25	0.09	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.00

at ≈ 100 kHz the RMS error is $< 3\%$ and at 200 kHz it is $< 0.3\%$. Thus, the truncation effects appear to become negligible (i.e., $|H(f)|$ and $|H_w(f)|$ are essentially the same) when the cutoff frequency exceeds the reciprocal of the truncation time; that is, when $f_{CO} > (t_T)^{-1} = c_T/x_T$, where c_T is the speed of sound in the transducer. For the ceramic and lithium niobate transducers mentioned above, the values of c_T/x_T are 200 kHz and 400 kHz, respectively.

Figure 2 contains example plots of the magnitude spectra $|H(f)|$ and $|H_w(f)|$ for $f_{CO} = 50$ kHz. The expected rippling due to the time domain truncation, and corresponding frequency domain convolution with the $W(f)$ sinc function, is evident in $|H_w(f)|$.

Figure 2 - Example plots of the magnitude spectra $|H(f)|$ (solid) and $|H_w(f)|$ (dashed) at $f_{CO} = 50$ kHz for the 0.5- μ s Gaussian pulse, $p_t(t)$.

III. CONCLUSION

When a thick piezoelectric disk transducer is used to generate a broadband transient pulse for the purpose of measuring the frequency response of a miniature ultrasonic hydrophone, there are two factors that limit the low frequency range. The first is related to the negative capacitance that appears in the transducer equivalent circuit, and it results in a transducer time constant equal to the reciprocal of $2\pi f_T$. For frequencies much greater than f_T (say, $f > 10f_T$), the negative capacitance and time constant can be ignored, in which case the spectrum of the pressure pulse radiated from the front face is proportional to that of the transducer excitation voltage.

The second factor is due to the truncation or windowing of the hydrophone voltage pulse necessitated by the finite measurement time available, x_T/c_T . For a narrow Gaussian pulse, it was shown that the actual and windowed hydrophone response spectra were essentially the same when the -3 dB high-pass cutoff frequency of the hydrophone was greater than approximately c_T/x_T . This conclusion has been shown to be valid for other pulse types and durations as well when a rectangular window is used [7].

For a piezoceramic disk of practical dimensions, the two factors both result in a frequency range that extends down to approximately 200 kHz. However, for lithium niobate, c_T/x_T dominates and results in a lower limit of about 400 kHz.

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